

23nm: Case study of Data Art Research as a model for practice in Data Art & Science

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Figure 1: Still from *23nm*, data art / stereoscopic digital animation video

ABSTRACT

As machine learning systems are rapidly changing our world, the role of data science as a discipline is elevated. However, existing approaches in science communication and data visualization are not sufficient to address the complexity of such systems and the profoundly changing relationship between humankind and data. We introduce the “Data Art & Science” (DAS) project in which the role of art as an integral part in the discourse about data is investigated through a series of commissioned art projects and close monitoring of their creation process and impact. For this paper, we propose a Data Art Research model and use it to discuss one of these art projects, *23nm*. We aim to show the value in creating a system to reason about DAS and position the latter as a new way of approaching data-reliant projects in academia and industry to increase the quality of public knowledge and discourse.

KEYWORDS

Scientific Visualizations, Data Journalism and Animated Documentary, Data Visualizations, Generative Art, Real-time CG

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1 INTRODUCTION

For the Data Art & Science Project 2023 (Ars Electronica Futurelab /Toyota Coniq Alpha) [3], several artists were commissioned to create a series of demo projects for Deep Space 8K¹ at the intersection of data art — art that uses data as a medium and/or source material — and data science.

The goal was to highlight the profound impact of data on our understanding of the world and emphasize the importance of uncovering and sharing stories hidden within data. This paper shares the broader research focus underlying the project and how it applies to one of the artworks realized, *23nm* by Peter Holzkorn, who is also one of the authors of this text.

The project aimed to investigate the transformative power of intertwining data art with data science, and the potential of artistic storytelling and possible impacts to the audience. The two disciplines could form a relationship that blends critical thinking and emotional experience for the recipients and creators. The concept of “Art Thinking” [29] played a crucial role as well as the ability of individual artistic perspectives in uncovering insights beyond traditional scientific methods. Another focal point was the potential to engage a broader audience through experiential narratives. For this connection of data art and data science, the term “Data Art & Science” (DAS) was established.

The research methodologies employed in DAS cover analysis of research processes and artistic language, project classification, and discussion of the relationship between art and science. The research accompanying the production began with a comparative analysis of existing projects, forming the basis for a step-by-step creation process - the Data Art Research Cycle. Beside the artistic research and production process of the creators involved, the developed artworks underwent thorough reflection via a series of interviews, following the steps of the cycle.

The artworks realized are “Intro: Who owns the Data?” by Ars Electronica Futurelab, “one who suffers” by quadrature [30], “— 寸 Issun” by Akiko Nakayama [28], “23nm” by Peter Holzkorn (Ars Electronica Futurelab) [17], “MOTHER FLUCTUATION” by Akira Wakita [38], and “Harmony Lost” by Arno Deutschbauer (Ars Electronica Futurelab), and this paper offers detailed insights in the creation of “23nm”. Two of the artworks, including “23nm”, use stereoscopic vision, and all except “Issun” are fully based on computer-generated graphics.

¹Immersive projection space and VR environment featuring active stereoscopic vision at Ars Electronica Center in Linz, Austria

Within the larger project the artworks serve as case studies, offering transparency into the creative process. Like in a cookbook, the aim was to reveal the ingredients and recipes employed by artists, providing a comprehensive view of their approach to working with data, detailing the components, tools, and processes involved in the commissioned projects, including extensive interviews with the artists before starting the work, during the production process and after the project presentation.

2 A MODEL FOR DATA ART RESEARCH

2.1 Relationship of DAS and Data Disciplines

Frameworks of thinking about Data Art and Science need to be positioned in relation to existing disciplines: Data science involves collecting, analysing, and interpreting large data sets using statistical and computational methods, requiring expertise in mathematics, computer science, and domain-specific knowledge. Its goal is to describe and utilize complex data. In contrast, data art has the ability to communicate and question socially relevant topics, emotions and ideas. It uses data in digital works to inform about and sensitize to socio-political issues [13]. Another relevant discipline is data visualization, the process of representing data graphically for easy understanding and interpretation [36]. It allows researchers to communicate complex data in a way that is accessible to a wide audience. Unlike art, however, its purpose is typically clear and direct communication of data.

Data Art & Science (“DAS”) combines the strengths of all three disciplines to create a more nuanced and multi-layered way of viewing and communicating the data than any singular approach. The key lies in the artistic strategy that forms knowledge by experience. Dewey describes art as an experience [11] and his considerations played a crucial part in the definitions of art-based research, artistic research or any other collaborative and/or trans-disciplinary practices in the Art-Science context [16, 19, 27]. However, the unique potential of DAS lies not in the addition of the opposite qualities of different disciplines, but in their common potential to contextualize social, cultural and political phenomena, to make them understandable and thus to perceive them as changeable. Manovich [24] describes Data (Science) as a means to understand the world, and explores and explains it against the background of art history and the humanities. Following this thought, it is key that we do not see DAS as a new form of data science or data art but a specific way to look at works of data art that step into an exchange with data science and data visualization and open the potential for a deep real-life impact on the world, not least because many data art projects inherently carry a “call to action” related to the subject of their data.

The research process connected to DAS also highlights the potential of cross-sectoral collaborations to create diverse and impactful artistic interpretations of data. The discursive relationship between knowledge creation, transfer, and embodiment is a key aspect of DAS, building on art practice as research [16] and project-based research [4, 5].

2.2 Methodology: The Data Art Research Cycle

Our research started with a comparative analysis of a selection of existing Data Art & Science projects which are well-documented regarding their process of creation and publication, and which fit to DAS in their structure and theme [1, 2, 12, 14, 14, 26, 31, 34, 35]. We looked at them regarding their production process and artistic language used, ranging from literal to metaphoric and from concrete to abstract. We classified projects based on their relevance to human-, society-, or planet-centredness, as well as their orientation toward posing questions, offering solutions, or already providing tangible implementations in society.

From the patterns of production of these works, and from an understanding of the research process in other (scientific) disciplines, we constructed a “Data Art Research Cycle”. No single model can encompass all forms of research, but there are ways to structure the steps common to many research problems, including phases of finding the research question, reviewing existing knowledge, assembling a toolkit, collecting data, processing data, and critically discussing the results [21]. There are also commonalities between scientific research and the newer concept of artistic research [7, 8], including the purpose to attain and communicate knowledge, and a critical and open character [16]. With this in mind, we propose our cyclical model as a step towards reasoning about data art research and its processes and methods. The goal is to foster exchange about data art and data art research, especially with stakeholders that are not from an artistic background.

The steps of the model were based on the above-mentioned commonalities in different types of research, and informed by the documentation of the case studies. We further interviewed the artists who created the works for the DAS project at critical points of the creation process and used the insights to test and refine the model. The steps of the Data Art Research Cycle are (see fig. 2):

- (1) **Observations:** Artistic curiosity is sparked by data material, which leads to creative inquiries.
- (2) **Questions:** The initial observations lead to creative questions that drive further exploration of the data and associated phenomena.
- (3) **Investigation:** Artists delve into the data, sometimes supplementing it with additional sources to gain deeper insights into the subject, while making connections to other fields and artworks.
- (4) **Envision:** Artists begin to formulate their artistic concepts and sketches, considering both content and form, as well as the intended user experience and audience reception. Some artists may use storyboards or other tools to develop their ideas.
- (5) **Experiment:** An experimental phase often precedes the final production, with the result representing an iteration of a series of experiments. Many artists work with prototypes

Figure 2: Data Art Research Cycle

and engage in an ongoing cycle of selection, refinement, and revision.

- (6) Production: While there may be overlap between the experimental and production phases, artists typically enter a stage where they actively work on creating the final piece to be exhibited or presented to the public.
- (7) Conclusion: Artists draw conclusions based on the final work, reflecting on its contextualization, exhibition, and the ensuing discourse around the piece.
- (8) Contextualization: This involves considering how the work fits within the specific framework of the exhibition event and its presentation within the context of the show (topic, other artists, narrative).
- (9) Exhibition: This step focuses on the considerations and implications of the work's presentation in the specific exhibition setting, including factors like location, presentation, and audience interaction.
- (10) Discourse: Ongoing discussion and theoretical exploration of the exhibited artwork, as well as of related texts and audience feedback.
- (11) New Questions: Presentation and discourse often spark new creative questions, which subsequently influence the artist's next work.

This is a theoretical and technical approach to the creation process, and its applicability may vary for individual artworks. In the following sections, the steps in realizing a particular work are described, based on the interviews with the artist and their additional reflection of their process after familiarizing themselves with the model.

3 23NM

In this section, we investigate *23nm* with respect to the model we proposed, and discuss how the latter can be used to reason about a work in this field.

3.1 Project Description and Data Subject

23nm is a magnifying look at how we can gather data about the minute and microscopic matter we manufacture with our mobility. Though practically invisible, nanoparticles impact our bodies in critical ways. Measurements taken in real city-traffic situations envelop the viewer as swarms of particular structures, transferring mass and volume to shape, form and colour. What if we could know the substance of the air we breathe so clearly everywhere, all the time? What if such measurements were as ubiquitous as traffic data, and could become, like distance, speed and stress, integral in the thoughts of our collective navigation systems?

- *23nm* artist statement

23nm is a digital animation featuring three separate "scenes" that depict virtual generative sculptures from datasets of particulate matter measurements of car exhaust emissions in several European cities.

The data was provided by researchers from Technical University Graz who had been part of the "City Air Remote Emission Sensing" (CARES) project. The project's goal is to "investigate contactless measurement of vehicle exhaust emission" [10], meaning that the measurements can be done at fixed or mobile stations in real-life traffic rather than in the laboratory. During that project's research, in many cases the measured parameters included counts of particulate matter down to 23 nanometres (which is the lower size boundary cut-off in the Diffusion Charging method employed [33]). Such particles between 23nm and 300nm are in this case (and within the context of CARES) called "nanoparticles" and are the main parameter of the data used in the artwork.

The nanoparticles emitted in traffic are of urgent interest to humans because of well-known health risks associated with exposure to them, not only regarding cardiovascular and respiratory diseases [9, 23] but also potential effects on other parts of the body such as the endocrine system, immune system and nervous system [39]. In the latter case, the smallness of the particles has yielded innovative treatment strategies because such particles, when deployed in a medical context, can effectively cross the blood-brain barrier to deliver drugs [22], but this implies the potential for hazards to the brain caused by involuntary exposure to nanoparticles of various origins.

In the course of the CARES measurements, there were two kinds of experimental setup:

- Stationary remote emission sensing: Stations were set up over several days in four major European cities. The exhaust gases of passing cars passed through the sensors and the concentrations of particulate matter (among other parameters) were measured.
- Plume chasing: Sensing equipment was placed on vehicles that followed certain other vehicles over longer distances, enabling the researchers to evaluate the emission composition of a single vehicle across different engine states and environments. This was done only in one European country, inside major cities and along long-distance road travel between cities.

In both cases, the researchers had the authority to automatically process licence plate information via computer vision and cross-reference the information with vehicle registration databases. Only anonymized personal data was provided to the researchers, but information such as vehicle brand, model, make, engine type, emission class and most recent mileage record was available and associated with the measured parameters. In some cases, especially in the course of the plume chasing sequences, violations of permissible emission characteristics were detected, due to defects or intentional circumvention of particle filters.

3.2 The Beginning: From Observation to Investigation

In the initial phases of **Observation**, **Questions** and **Investigation** the nature of the data was discussed and in the course of several meetings (some of which stretched into the later phases of producing the work) the artist acquired additional knowledge about the meaning of the data.

The artist identified the following themes as most relevant and interesting:

- Nanoparticles may adversely affect human health in many ways, some of which are not yet fully understood
- Nanoparticle measurements in real traffic provide a picture of the impact on air pollution that can be more precise and relevant than laboratory measurements; thus, research in the area of remote emission sensing is important
- Advances in remote emission sensing can help us attain a clearer picture of the composition of the air we breathe in different environments, and support policy decisions; it can also help identify violations of existing regulation
- The automated connection of remote emission characteristics to car registrations demonstrated in the measurement series indicates the trend that increasingly many aspects of the daily behaviour of humans can be evaluated live and traced back to individuals and personal responsibility, raising philosophical and ethical questions
- Based on an understanding of pollution relevance and sensing technologies, we can imagine scenarios where such measurements become more pervasive, allowing us to construct systems which help us react to air quality characteristics and automatically suggest behaviours to counteract problematic concentrations (such as is already the case in systems that help drivers avoid traffic congestion)

The themes could be used to phrase several questions to guide the process of creating a work of data art:

- What can we learn from this data that is new, given common knowledge about air pollution, diesel scandals, etc.?
- How does it feel to learn more about these invisible dangers? How much did we already know, and how does the perception shift if we can relate to it aesthetically?
- Is there anything about the data that would lead to change in our behaviour if we were more aware of it?
- What attributes does data have that is associated with nanometre scales? How do we think about matter too small for us to perceive, but very much solid and visible? What does it do to our imagination?

The artist would address these questions according to his personal understanding of Data Art:

The artist's personal approach to the meaning of the data informs the general aesthetics, but the artwork itself is not fully determined by the artist. The viewer can choose how much they attempt to "decrypt" the visual artefacts to "read" the data, and how much they simply interact with the work as an aesthetic experience that may connect to their personal experiences and emotions. Thus, the "message" of the underlying data can be transmitted on different layers, far from "pure" data visualization.

Observation and **Questions** required conversations with the TU Graz researchers and the study of topics related to the data, such as the used sensor technologies, potential health effects and basics of emission regulation. **Investigation** could be started, but needed additional work with the data itself to lead to the next phase.

3.3 Data Exploration and Prototypes: From Investigation to Experimentation

As a first approach, the two kinds of data (*stationary* and *chasing*) were sorted and viewed. Jupyter Notebooks [18] along with common plotting libraries were used to visualize the scale and scope of the different parameters (initially, not just particles) as well as detect incomplete or inconsistently labelled data sets. Once the data was better understood, car makes and models were further analysed in bar graphs to reconstruct the type of traffic that was captured in the stationary series, and to find patterns that could be interesting for the visual concept. Of the *chasing* series, the unique additional information was the geographical tagging, so the map visualization service mapbox [25] was used to gain an initial understanding of this data, and already explore interesting spatial patterns. From these processes of investigation, possible visual perspectives were discussed in ideation meetings with other artists/researchers associated with the larger project, and a storyboard was sketched.

The story structure would be split into an intro and two scenes: The intro would draw the viewers into the nanoscopic scales with a direct size visualization. The main scenes would show different manifestations of the two types of datasets, each a living virtual sculpture employing generative real-time graphics processes parametrized with key aspects of the data. Finally, the second scene should expand into a hint toward the future vision of hypothetical ubiquitous measurements of such data. Both scenes should be visually fascinating and utilize the potential for immersion in abstract spaces provided by Deep Space 8K.

Investigation of the data was done with standard toolkits of data science and visualization, and helped the artist become familiar with the data. These steps already allowed the artist to **Envision** scenes and **Experiment** with visual aspects (such as cartographical plots) before approaching the production phases.

3.4 Iterative Making: Experiment & Production

From this point on, the data was prepared, named and sanitized to be consistently read by the application responsible for generating the visual outcome, which was developed in the Unity [37] graphics engine. Fascinating visual complexity can be achieved by processes which use algorithmic strategies to create visual structures that grow, multiply and change according to particular rules; such approaches are a type of “generative art” or “computer-generated art” [6, 15]. In both main scenes of the artwork, the virtual data sculptures should grow and change according to the rules of particle systems, a common technique in computer graphics, and particularly fitting for a work about nanoparticles.

For *stationary*, various experiments were made with the characteristics of the particle system, including materials, shapes and positioning in space. Finally, to balance the tactility of particle clouds with the possibility of relational understanding (if not direct legibility), the stations in different cities were positioned in adjacent “tunnels” through which the particle systems stream, particle numbers and sizes informed by the emission time series.

For *chasing*, the topography of emissions along roads, stripped of contextual map information, was mapped to continuously growing spherical bodies, like a bone or root structure, but with the colours and unending enlargement reminiscent of cancerous agglomerations. This growth, following the data trails directly, was, for the final shot, morphed into a glowing sculpture in which the structures were stochastically expanded and multiplied, to point at the potential future of ubiquitous sensing.

The development of both scenes was a loop of experimentation and production, with many variations of mapping the data to different colours, shapes and movements, and careful selection of a balance between following aesthetic curiosity and maintaining a system that can be interpreted by the viewer. The visual articulation also changed as the data became more familiar and better understood: Inconsistent presence of different vehicle registration data points across datasets from different locations informed the decision to show only the most salient parameters (time and place of sample, model and make of the car); limitation of plume chasing geotags to sparse subsets of large cities led the artist from a cartographic approach towards a more sculptural one.

These two phases, taking by far the biggest amount of time in the making of the artwork, are iterative and nonlinear – important aspects of creativity [32]. They also continuously reshape the designs devised in the **Envision** phase. In this case, the fundamental structure was not changed, but if the story had not come together as intended or if the artist had felt that it did not flow naturally from the data any more, it would have warranted to go back one step further and re-envision the project.

3.5 Final Shape: From Conclusion to New Questions

At the point at which the final four-minute animation was presented in stereo vision, and complemented by a custom soundscape created by Arno Deutschbauer (who also created one of the

other DAS projects), the process led the artist to the following insights, connected to both development of the work and the observation of audience behaviour and following discussions in the exhibition environment:

- (1) Compared to some other artworks mentioned in section 1, the first half of *23nm* features rather concrete interpretations. The clarity of this was chosen partly due to the aspect of linking emission characteristics with vehicle data. Furthermore, the scene was generally regarded by viewers as easy to understand, and while it may straddle the border between art and visualization, in the context of the project it filled an important position on the spectrum between the very informative/direct and the fully abstract/interpretive that was meant to be illustrated.
- (2) Based on conversations with audience members, the second (more abstracted) scene was generally felt to be more captivating: Even though the data could be less easily interpreted, people were more emotionally activated by it. Konečni [20] describes “aesthetic awe” as a “mixture of [...] joy and fear”, caused by a stimulus combining several factors, including a psychophysical dimension. This dimension is clearly present in the large-scale, immersive view of an unknown growing structure, while the viewer’s knowledge about the toxic character of the data subject combined with threatening, stark black-on-orange colour scheme and a dramatic soundscape may contribute to the dynamic between visual fascination (joy) and fear.
- (3) Regarding the data itself, it was both surprising (1) how much can be extracted from current sensor technology in combination with digitalized vehicle data, and (2) how heterogeneous and “messy” the measurements were, with physical limitations and changes in the recording structure making it difficult to directly compare data from different times and locations, and leading the artist to focus on the parts of the data that appeared more interesting and reliable for a visual interpretation without skewing the underlying truth.
- (4) After the project presentation, the TU Graz researcher who had supplied and explained the data was also interviewed for the DAS project report. Regarding *23nm*, he expressed his appreciation of the collaboration and the innovative approach in merging scientific data with artistic expression for social impact, in line with his view that such collaboration between art and science is highly beneficial, in particular regarding knowledge dissemination and broadening the public’s comprehension of complex scientific topics to the benefit of society as a whole. While this response is great encouragement for further DAS projects, it does not explicitly mention if and how the process may have influenced the approach the CARES researchers may take in the future, or how it allowed the experts on the data to see it in a new light – an aspect that the artist would like to address with more emphasis in future work.

These insights, in particular the different impact of the two main scenes, can be regarded as a starting point for the conceptualization of the next data art projects. A dramaturgy of conveying theme

and context, building understanding and creating potential for emotional impact and further reflection through “aesthetic awe” could be one type of recipe for data art which could be more consciously employed in the next project.

In scientific research, conclusions normally precede a sharing of the results with the wider community. In Data Art Research, **Conclusion, Contextualization, Exhibition and Discourse** form another iterative process. For *23nm*, questions regarding how we think about substances on a nanometre scale can only start to be answered through dialogue about the work when it is exhibited, for example.

3.6 Technology and Techniques of Animation

23nm was conceived as generative, but non-interactive and based only on an existing dataset from the past. Data parameters to be used for animation properties (such as particle count) in Unity and “played back” along the corresponding timestamps so that the animation progresses along the timelines of real measurements. From the values, parameters such as visual particle birth rate are calculated and injected into *Visual Effects Graphs*, a Unity feature for designing particle systems and other visual effects using a node-based visual programming system. This is combined with *Shader Graphs*, a node-based system for implementing shaders (offering extra flexibility through custom HLSL-based functions), especially suitable for the complex High-Definition Render Pipeline (HDRP). The combination of these systems is a relatively new option in the engine (introduced in 2021). In both cases, the node-based character appeals to the experimental visual approach that was central to the project. For scene build-ups and transitions, a system of coroutines for flexible timing design was created and applied to scene objects and post-processing layers.

During the development process, it was decided that the application should render stereoscopic visual output suitable for the Deep Space 8K environment. Since Unity has not supported this for several years and a commercial third-party solution was beyond the scope of the budget, it was decided, for the purpose of the initial presentations, to pre-render a stereoscopic video and play it back using an existing stereoscopic media player. A side-by-side stereo image was generated using an open-source plug-in for Unity, visual output of the application was captured using two additional PCs with capture cards (since no suitable screen-recording tool was capable of capturing 2 x 4k resolution) and the captured videos were recombined using Adobe After Effects. The final output, a 2 x 4k side-by-side stereo video file, is the format in which *23nm* is currently available for stereoscopic presentation. This may soon be complemented by a live version of the application itself with a new custom middleware (under development) allowing stereo vision with Unity.

3.7 Review of the Analysis

Even though it becomes apparent that even within the Data Art Research Cycle the phases are not linear, but form smaller sub-cycles, we could still easily explain the important aspects at each stage. While all phases could also exist in art research that is not deeply informed by data, many processes, especially those of investigation and experimentation, have complex interdisciplinary

aspects that are particularly suitable for being discussed using our model.

There are some stages that carried more weight in the specific case of *23nm*. “Envision”, “Experiment” and “Production” took the most time because they involved the technical steps of making the artwork, and arguably formed a cycle in itself; this loop to a lesser degree even extended back to “Questions” and “Investigation”. The steps between “Conclusion” and “Discourse”, on the other hand, formed their own logical unit. At the time of writing, the work is increasingly shown in the regular museum programme rather than only at special presentations, meaning that the sub-loop of these latter steps is still gaining momentum.

23nm proved to be an interesting case study because it progresses from an intro of direct science communication over a scene that sits at the border between data visualization and data art to a third act of a highly abstract interpretation. We therefore expect the model to work well across the full spectrum of data art.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The Data Art & Science Project 2023 not only showed the creative synergy between art and science but also offered a comprehensive resource for those interested in the dynamic field of DAS. It revealed a surprising diversity in artistic approaches, proving the worth of data art for societal reflection. The established process cycle and research plan emerged as robust tools, adapting to the dynamic interplay between art, technology, and science.

Application of the Data Art Research Cycle to a review of *23nm* has shown that it is a useful model to discuss a work in the field of DAS, where disciplinary boundaries are fluid and established methods of analysis are not directly applicable. It has further been shown how an artwork in this field can and should be discussed with regard to its balance of portraying data and creating emotional impact through its choice of aesthetics, a relationship which is central to DAS. One aspect of the process-oriented approach that should be regarded critically is that the generic character of the chosen model means that it could be applied to most artistic projects. From the artists’ interviews, it has become evident that the cycle is indeed a continuous loop, but also involving sub-cycles of singular steps. Each step can be an iteration, not all steps may be necessary, and their order might vary.

As the larger project of DAS research is still ongoing, we may well revise the Data Art Research Cycle. The work developed within the 2024 edition of the DAS project is focusing on participatory data surrounding the topics of cultural heritage exploration and personal data archives for empathy. We want to explore the integration of participatory strategies and audience interaction, involving multiple individuals supplying pieces of data and merging them into comprehensive datasets. The goal is to increase the public involvement in data generation and artistic creation, as well as to enhance the societal relevance of the projects. In these upcoming projects, the insights gained from the case study presented in this paper can be used to inform the dialogue between the different stakeholders involved in the process. It is also of interest how this model could reveal challenges and opportunities particular to a more participatory concept.

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